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TAX REVENUE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH NEXUS IN NIGERIA: AN AUTOREGRESSIVE DISTRIBUTED LAG APPROACH

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Company Income Tax (CIT), Value Added Tax (VAT), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL), Time series analysis

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Abstract

This study examined the nexus between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, the study evaluates the effect of Company Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT) on the growth path of the Nigerian economy. The ex-post facto research design was employed; time series data were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria, National Bureau of Statistics, and the Federal Inland Revenue Service. The study's employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag Approach (ARDL) bound test and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test. Other variables were integrated of order one $I(1)$ while inflation rate is stationary at level and the variables has long run relationship (cointegrated). The findings revealed that company income tax has positive significant effect on Nigeria's economic growth while value added tax has negative significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. The study recommends that government should diversify into other sectors and be transparent enough to account for the revenue it generates through Company Income Tax and Value Added Tax by investing massively in the provision of infrastructural facilities which are capable of creating job opportunities and enabling environment for entrepreneurship and innovation.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Every responsible government has as its primary responsibility the provision of adequate public goods and services that are capable of raising the living standard of its citizens. The government's ability to carry out these tasks is largely dependent on the amount of revenue it generates through various means. Taxation is one of the most viable sources of funds for providing necessary services to the general public in a certain geographical region. Governments strive to accomplish their responsibilities by providing public education, adequate roads, sanitation, security, health-care facilities, and power, among other things. The availability of these public goods and services is what drives and supports the economy's growth (Karumba, 2016).

Surprisingly, the following studies suggest that the tax revenue from company income tax (CIT) and value added tax (VAT) in Nigeria has been increasing over time:

[Onwuchekwa and Aruwa \(2014\)](#) examined the effects of value added tax on the economic growth of Nigeria. The Ordinary Least Squares approach was utilized to examine the given assumptions. The findings indicate that Value Added Tax (VAT) plays a substantial role in the overall tax revenue generated by the government, hence contributing to the economic growth of Nigeria. The growth in value-added tax (VAT) revenue exhibited a constant upward trend, albeit lacking in significant acceleration. In order to enhance tax revenue, it is imperative to augment the money derived from Value Added Tax (VAT).

[Doki and Sule \(2015\)](#) explored the implications of corporation income tax as a potential source of alternative financing for sustainable development in Nigeria. The research utilized the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method and Co integration Test to examine the enduring association between company income tax and revenue generation in Nigeria. The analysis was conducted for the period spanning from 1987 to 2013. The findings indicate that a one percent increase in the contribution of Corporate Income Tax (CIT) leads to a corresponding revenue generating increase of 0.42%.

[Izedonmi and Okunbor \(2014\)](#) showed that VAT revenue and total revenue account for a significant portion of the variations in GDP in Nigeria. The introduction of Value Added Tax (VAT) in Nigeria in 1993 was implemented by the Federal Government as a replacement for the Sales Tax system. The objective was to enhance the government's revenue sources and allocate cash towards developmental initiatives aimed at expediting economic growth. This study empirically investigates the impact of Value Added Tax (VAT) on the economic development of Nigeria. The research involved examining time series data on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), VAT Revenue, Total Tax Revenue, and Total (Federal Government) Revenue from the years 1994 to 2010. The data was obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The analysis employed both simple regression analysis and descriptive statistical methods. The results of the study indicate that there is a substantial correlation between VAT Revenue accounts and total revenue, accounting for up to 92% of the observed fluctuations in GDP in Nigeria. There is a positive association between VAT Revenue and GDP, albeit it is statistically insignificant.

Therefore, this study is set out to investigate the impact of company income tax (CIT) and value added tax (VAT) on the Nigerian economic growth, proxied by gross domestic product (GDP) from 1986 to 2020. This research is significant because it will contribute to the growth of local evidence on the effect of tax revenue on economic growth in developing market economy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Issues

Value Added Tax (VAT)

Various authors and writers have defined the term "value-added tax" in various ways and in this study adopted the definition opined by [Abata \(2014\)](#). According to him "Value-Added Tax is a consumption tax where the tax burden is borne by the consumers." He noted that the tax burden is passed on from the manufacturer to the wholesaler, then to the retailer, and lastly to the consumer. As a result, the only way to avoid paying VAT is to stop purchasing and using vatable products and services. A vatable person, on the other hand, is someone who exchanges vatable goods and services for money.

Company Income Tax (CIT)

According to Appah (2010), all established firms in Nigeria must pay Company Income Tax on earnings earned in, derived from, brought into, or received in the country. It also includes taxes on non-resident firms doing business in Nigeria, which are paid by both private and public limited liability corporations. The Companies Income Tax Act (CITA) of 1979 was enacted to replace the Income Tax Management Act of 1961, which had been in place since 1961. The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) administers and collects this tax, which contributes significantly to the government's revenue profile. Such gains are considered to have accrued in Nigeria regardless of where they originated (globally) or whether they were transported into or received in Nigeria (Ugochukwu and Azubike, 2016). Earnings from any trade or business, rent on property used, dividends, interest, royalties, discounts, charges, annuities, fees for services given, and other sources of annual profits or gains are all examples. As a result, both Nigerian and international corporations are subject to the Company Income Tax Act in Nigeria.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is defined by the Central Bank of Nigeria (2010) as the monetary worth of goods and services produced in an economy over a period of time, regardless of the nationality of those who produced them. It is commonly estimated without taking into account capital expenditures (or deductions for depreciation).

Review of Empirical Literature

Using ordinary least squares, Olugbemi, Bassey, and Michael (2020) investigated the impact of taxation on economic growth. Using GDP as an index, the result shows that there is a positive relationship between tax revenue and economic growth. Examining the data further revealed that tax income had a favorable impact on the Nigeria's economic growth using ARDL. Bingilar and Preye (2020) looked at the influence of the Value Added Tax on Nigerian economic growth from 2009 to 2018. For data analysis, the study used multiple regression analysis with ordinary Least Square (OLS) econometric technique. The study's findings demonstrated that value added tax had a positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria, and that any rise in value added tax will almost certainly result in an increase in Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). From 1995 to 2015, Edewusi and Ajayi (2019) investigated the relationship between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. Using Multiple Regression Analysis, Co-integration, and other post-estimation tests, the data was evaluated to determine the short and long run effects of the variables. The results showed that tax revenue stated in terms of petroleum profit tax, company income tax, and value added tax will influence the level of national output in the long and short run. Using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique, Lyndon and Paymaster (2016) looked at the influence of company income tax and value-added tax on economic growth (as measured by GDP) in Nigeria from 2005 to 2014. The findings revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between corporate income tax, value added tax, and RGDP.

Akhor and Ekundayo (2016) examined the relationship between indirect tax income and economic development in Nigeria. The study was conducted over a 21-year period (1993–2013). The data was analyzed using correlation analysis, co-integration tests, and regression analysis using the Error Correction Model (ECM). In particular, it was discovered that, despite its negative nature, the association between VAT and economic development was strong, but the relationship between customs and excise charges was modest.

From 1994 to 2018, [Mukolu and Ogodor \(2021\)](#) empirically evaluated the impact of Value Added Tax (VAT) on Nigerian economic growth. The data was analyzed using a unit root test and the Augmented Dickey Fuller technique of analysis. The empirical conclusion reveals that the value of VAT has a significant positive impact on Nigeria's economic growth (RGDP). The studies also demonstrated that value added tax had a positive and significant impact on Nigeria's total revenue, and hence on the country's economic growth and development.

Theoretical Framework

The Economic Principle and Revenue Productivity Theory underpinned this study:

Keynes Theory of Growth

The development of various growth theories, each claiming to explain the mechanics of growth, has resulted from interest in growth issues. However, in the context of this study, Keynes' growth theory provides the theoretical foundation because it explains how growth can be achieved by increasing government expenditure, whereas government expenditure is a function of revenue, of which company income tax (CIT) and value added tax (VAT) form part of the source.

Increased government spending, according to Keynes, leads to a greater economic growth. Long-term full employment is demonstrated by the theory, which requires two key requirements to be met: the ratio of investment to income must equal the full employment savings ratio, and the economy's rate of growth must equal the natural rate of growth. The insufficiency of aggregate effective demand, according to Keynes, is a critical component that might explain for an economy's stagnation and unemployment. The remedy to the problem of economic stagnation, according to Keynes, was to stimulate aggregate demand by enormous increases in government spending ([Alfred, 2005](#)). Government expenditures, on the other hand, are dependent on revenue generated from taxation, including company income tax and value added tax.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was used to conduct this research. This strategy addresses the issue of drifting series while also allowing us to determine the model's short-run and long-term relationships. This study identified both dependent variable (economic growth proxied by GDP) and independent variables which include Company Income Tax and Value Added Tax. It focuses on the individual effect of Company Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT) on Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Thus, GDP depends on Company Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT) as well as other control variables, to avoid over stating the influence of the two pivot variables of interest of the study within the period under study.

In terms of functional relationship, we have this stated as

$$GDP = f(CIT, VAT, INF, EXR, GEX) \quad \dots (1)$$

The generalized ARDL model is stated as

$$Y_t = \gamma_{0i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \dots (2)$$

Where Y'_t is a vector and the variables in the $(X'_t)'$ are allowed to be purely $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ or cointegrated, β and δ are the coefficients. γ is the constant; $i=1, \dots, k$; p, q are optimal lag orders; ε_{it} is a vector of the error terms.

The Conditional ARDL Model (6 variables)

The co-integrating relationship among variables of the model following the ARDL equation is stated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Delta \text{LGDP}_t \\
&= \emptyset + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LCIT}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i \Delta \text{LVAT}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \vartheta_i \Delta \text{INF}_{t-1} \\
&+ \sum_{i=1}^q \mu_i \Delta \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGEX}_{t-1} + \varphi_1 \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \varphi_2 \text{LCIT}_{t-1} + \varphi_3 \text{LVAT}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varphi_4 \text{INF}_{t-1} + \varphi_5 \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \varphi_6 \text{LGEX}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (3)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Delta \text{LCIT}_t \\
&= \emptyset + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta \text{LCIT}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i \Delta \text{LVAT}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \vartheta_i \Delta \text{INF}_{t-1} \\
&+ \sum_{i=1}^q \mu_i \Delta \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGEX}_{t-1} + \varphi_1 \text{LCIT}_{t-1} + \varphi_2 \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \varphi_3 \text{LVAT}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varphi_4 \text{INF}_{t-1} + \varphi_5 \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \varphi_6 \text{LGEX}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (4)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Delta \text{LVAT}_t \\
&= \emptyset + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta \text{LVAT}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i \Delta \text{LCIT}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \vartheta_i \Delta \text{INF}_{t-1} \\
&+ \sum_{i=1}^q \mu_i \Delta \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGEX}_{t-1} + \varphi_1 \text{LVAT}_{t-1} + \varphi_2 \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \varphi_3 \text{LCIT}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varphi_4 \text{INF}_{t-1} + \varphi_5 \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \varphi_6 \text{LGEX}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (5)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Delta \text{INF}_t \\
&= \emptyset + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta \text{INF}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i \Delta \text{LCIT}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \vartheta_i \Delta \text{LVAT}_{t-1} \\
&+ \sum_{i=1}^q \mu_i \Delta \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGEX}_{t-1} + \varphi_1 \text{INF}_{t-1} + \varphi_2 \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \varphi_3 \text{LCIT}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varphi_4 \text{LVAT}_{t-1} + \varphi_5 \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \varphi_6 \text{LGEX}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (6)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Delta \text{EXR}_t \\
&= \emptyset + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i \Delta \text{LCIT}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \vartheta_i \Delta \text{LVAT}_{t-1} \\
&+ \sum_{i=1}^q \mu_i \Delta \text{INF}_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta \text{LGEX}_{t-1} + \varphi_1 \text{EXR}_{t-1} + \varphi_2 \text{LGDP}_{t-1} + \varphi_3 \text{LCIT}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varphi_4 \text{LVAT}_{t-1} + \varphi_5 \text{INF}_{t-1} + \varphi_6 \text{LGEX}_{t-1} \\
&+ \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (7)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Delta LGEX_t \\
&= \emptyset + \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta LGEX_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i \Delta LCIT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \vartheta_i \Delta LVAT_{t-1} \\
&+ \sum_{i=1}^q \mu_i \Delta INF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta EXR_{t-1} + \varphi_1 LGEX_{t-1} + \varphi_2 LGDP_{t-1} + \varphi_3 LCIT_{t-1} \\
&+ \varphi_4 LVAT_{t-1} + \varphi_5 INF_{t-1} + \varphi_6 EXR_{t-1} \\
&+ \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (8)
\end{aligned}$$

As earlier stated, p and q are the ARDL model maximum lag orders for dependent and explanatory variables, respectively. The coefficients of the lagged variables represent the long run relationship, while the coefficients of the summations represent the short run model. The F-test is carried out on the joint null hypothesis that the coefficients of the lagged variables are zero. The hypothesis states that the coefficients of the lag level variables are zero i.e., there is no long run relationship among the series. This is defined by:

$$H_0: \varphi_1 = \varphi_2 = \varphi_3 = \varphi_4 = 0 \text{ (long run relationship does not exist)}$$

$$H_1: \varphi_1 \neq \varphi_2 \neq \varphi_3 \neq \varphi_4 \neq 0 \text{ (long run relationship exist)}$$

Decision Rule

1. If f-test value is greater than the upper bound, there is co-integration between the variables
2. If f-test is less than the lower bound, there is no co-integration between the variables
3. If f-test falls within the two bounds, the test is inconclusive.

Note that: if there is no co-integration, we specify the ARDL (long-run) Model

$$GDP_t = \emptyset + \delta LCIT_t + \beta LVAT_t + \vartheta INF_t + \mu EXR_t + \delta LGEX_t + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (9)$$

And if otherwise, we specify the Error correction (short-run) Model

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta LGDP_t = \emptyset + & \sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta LCIT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_i \Delta LVAT_{t-1} \\
& + \sum_{i=1}^q \vartheta_i \Delta INF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \mu_i \Delta EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \delta_i \Delta LGEX_{t-1} + \lambda ECT \\
& + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots (10)
\end{aligned}$$

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This study uses time series data to analyze the relationship between tax revenue (i.e. company income tax and value added tax) and gross domestic product of the Nigerian economy. Time series data analysis might produce spurious result most especially when they are non-stationary.

Pre-estimation Tests

To ensure robust and reliable results, we first perform unit root test to determine the integration order of each variable.

Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test

In testing for the stationarity of the variables, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) was used and the result of the tests were presented in Table 4.1.1

Table 1: Unit Root Test Result

Variable	ADF	Critical Value	Result
LGDP	-3.104001 (0.0360)	-2.615817***	I(1)
LCIT	-7.413247 (0.0000)	-2.615817 ***	I(1)
LVAT	-7.656206 (0,0000)	-2.615817***	I(1)
INF	-2.800406 (0.0688)	-2.614300 ***	I(0)
EXR	-3.949759 (0.0046)	-2.615817***	I(1)
LGEX	-7.934658 (0.0000)	-2.615817 ***	I(1)

Note: *, **, *** represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9.0

Table 4.1.1 depict unit root test result from our analysis, the result shows that, with the exception of inflation rate (INF), all other variables are not stationary at level but are subsequently differenced once and they became stationary. This, by implication, means they are order one I(1) variables or differenced stationary variables. Having found the variables are mixture of order one I(1) and order zero I(0) as well as none of the variables are integrated of a higher order. Hence, the appropriate model to determine the existence of Co-integration among the variables is ARDL model. This is necessary to avoid spurious regression as ARDL model cannot be applied on a variable that is higher than order one I(1). In the next stage, we would determine the lag length for our model.

Optimal Lag Length Selection

To determine the optimal lag length, the study applied unrestricted VAR. This is to enable the choice of appropriate lag for this study.

Table 2: VAR Output

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-394.9201	NA	1438.041	24.29819	24.57028	24.38974
1	-225.2918	267.2930*	0.454520*	16.19951	18.10415*	16.84036*
2	-188.3969	44.72117	0.542365	16.14527*	19.68246	17.33543

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9.0

From the result as shown in Table 4.1.2, all other selection criteria indicated lag one (1) whereas AIC indicated two (2) lags as the optimum lag length. AIC was selected based on the fact that this selection criterion has the minimum value compared to the other values of other selection criteria.

ARDL Bound Test

The ARDL bound test was carried out, after the appropriate lag length was determined, to ascertain whether the variables are Co-integrated or not.

Table 3: Bound Test

Dependent Variable	F-Statistics	No. of Variables	Co-integration	Remark
LGDP	$F_{LGDP} = 4.723837$	5	Yes	Estimate ECM
		Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
Critical Value		10%	2.26	3.35
		5%	2.62	3.79
		1%	3.41	4.68

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9.0

Table 4.1.3 revealed that F-statistics value (4.723837) is greater than the upper bound of 3.79 Pesaran critical values at 5% level. Hence we are 95 percent confident that, these variables have a long run relationship. That is they correlate the in long run. Having found the variables are co-integrated, it means there must be error correction model to determine the speed of adjustment in short run.

Model Estimation

Long Run Result

Table 4: Long Run Result

Dependent Variable: LGDP				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LCIT	0.168761	0.096753	1.744246	0.0957
LVAT	-0.163783	0.085477	-1.916098	0.0691
INF	-0.003469	0.004641	-0.747643	0.4630
EXR	-0.000576	0.000857	-0.671672	0.5091
LGEX	1.064989	0.175243	6.077227	0.0000
C	2.387323	0.859283	2.778272	0.0113

$R^2 = 0.999378$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.999053$, AIC = -2.534588, SIC = -1.990403, HQC = -2.351486
F-stat. = 3069.189 (0.000000), DW = 1.989810

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9.0

Table 4.2.1 depicts long run result obtained from our estimation. All other variables, with the exception of log of value added tax (LVAT), have the expected signs consistent with a priori expectation and in line with the. For instance, a one percent increase in company income tax (CIT) will lead to increase in economic growth by 0.1687 percent. A one percent increase in government expenditure (GEX), the economic growth will increase by 1.06 percent, all things being equal. This is so because increase of government expenditure will positively affect the gross domestic product of the economy. When exchange rate (EXR) increases by one percent, economic growth will decrease by 0.0006 percent. These results are consistent with economic theory. Furthermore, a one percent increase in inflation rate (INF) will translate to a decrease in economic growth by 0.0035 percent and a one percent increase in value added tax (VAT) will lead to a 0.1637 percent decrease in economic growth.

Short Run (Dynamic) Model for Tax Revenue and Economic Growth

Table 4.2.2 depicts the short-run estimate obtained from our analysis. The result of the analysis revealed that the lag value of Gross Domestic Product (LGDP) and Company Income Tax (CIT), government expenditure (GEX) exerted positive effect on economic growth (Gross Domestic Product) of Nigeria, whereas Inflation Rate (INF), value added tax (VAT) and exchange rate (EXR) have negative effects on economic growth in Nigeria, respectively.

Note that, the negative effect of value added tax (VAT) is not consistent with economic theory.

Table 5: Short-run (Dynamic) Model Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LGDP(-1))	0.408470	0.184525	2.213626	0.0381
D(LCIT)	0.181839	0.042914	4.237335	0.0004
D(LVAT)	-0.055713	0.028376	-1.963409	0.0630

D(INF)	-0.001343	0.000939	-1.430332	0.1673
D(INF)	0.002126	0.001091	1.948203	0.0649
D(EXR)	-0.000196	0.000291	-0.672778	0.5084
D(LGEX)	0.194722	0.091789	2.121413	0.0460
CointEq(-1)	-0.340164	0.129222	-2.632406	0.0156

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9.0

All these effects, with the exception of inflation rate (INF) and exchange rate (EXR,) are statistically significant at 10% as evidenced by their individual probability values. This, by implication, means a one percent increase in the previous value of gross domestic product (GDP), company income tax (CIT), and government expenditure (GEX) will lead to 0.4085 percent, 0.1818 percent and 0.1947 percent rise in real gross domestic product, respectively. Whereas at one percent increase in value added tax (VAT), inflation rate (INF) and exchange rate (EXR) will lead to 0.0557 percent, 0.0015 percent and 0.0002 percent decrease in real gross domestic product (GDP), respectively. Value added tax (VAT) has significant but negative impact on the economic growth of Nigeria. This finding is in line with the work of [Abdulsalam, Abubakar, and Ahmad, \(2020\)](#) and [Ibanichuka, Akani, and Ikebujo \(2016\)](#) who found a significant negative relationship between value added tax (VAT) and economic growth in Nigeria. Consequently, the error correction term (ECT) has expected negative sign and statistically significant at 5%. This reinforces the long run relationship among the variables in our Co-integration result. In case of any distortion in the economy, the error correction model indicating that the economy will correct itself from the disequilibrium toward the equilibrium at the rate of 34% per year.

Post Estimation Tests

Table 6: Post Estimation Results

Test	Statistical Value	Probability
Jarque-Bera	2.478133	0.289655
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM	0.022926	0.9774
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.626525	0.7866
Ramsey Reset	0.139267	0.7129

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 9.0

The study used post-estimation tests to determine if the estimated results were valid or not. The result presented in Table 4.3 the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation test shows that the model is free from serial correlation problem; the p-value is greater than 0.05% indicating the acceptance of the null hypothesis which states that there is no serial correlation. The normality test indicated that residuals are normally distributed as revealed by the probability value of the Jarque-Bera being greater than 0.05%; the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroscedasticity indicated that the residual is homoskedastic, as the p-value is greater than 0.05% hence, we accept the null hypothesis.

Cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMsq) are commonly used to test the stability of long run coefficients and short run dynamics. Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001) argued that the error correction model's stability must be evaluated. The graphs in figure 4.3.1 and figure 4.3.2 present the graph for both the CUSUM and CUSUM squares tests. The graphs indicate that our coefficients are stationary. Hence we cannot reject the null hypothesis since the plot is within the critical upper and lower bounds of the 5% significance level and also implies that the long-run coefficients are stable.

Figure 1: CUSUM coefficient stability graph**CONCLUSION**

This study adds to the ongoing discourse on the relationship between taxation and economic growth in Nigeria. The empirical findings underscore the complex dynamics between CIT, VAT, and economic growth, revealing potential trade-offs and opportunities for policy interventions. Effective fiscal policies that optimize tax revenue while minimizing adverse effects on economic growth are essential for Nigeria's sustainable development.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

The findings carry important policy implications and following recommendations were made:

- i. Policymakers should consider a balanced approach to taxation. While CIT may contribute to government revenue, its potential impact on private sector activity should be monitored and offset with targeted investment policies. On the other hand, VAT appears to have a relatively negative impact on economic growth, suggesting an efficient tax administration and prudent revenue allocation.

- ii. Government should transparently and judiciously account for the revenue it generates through Company Income Tax and Value Added Tax by investing massively in the provision of infrastructural facilities.
- iii. Government should diversify the economy. In so doing, revenue accrued to the government through Company Income Tax Value and Added Tax will be sufficient to be used in developing other sectors, especially other mineral resources and agricultural sector since the country has what it takes in terms of fertile land, favourable climate and work force, which will lead to economic growth.
- iv. To increase the government's revenue base, job opportunities should be developed, as well as enabling environment for entrepreneurship and innovation.
- v. And lastly, government should undertake a comprehensive reorganization of tax administrative machinery in order to minimize tax evasion and avoidance to a barest minimum.

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